

Warpage behaviour of discontinuous CF/PEEK thin plates

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Background

Discontinuous carbon UD tape (i.e. strand) thermoplastic composites have been used in the aerospace industry to produce intricate, net-shape parts with complex features.

Challenge: Residual stresses and warpage for thin parts

Objectives

- 1) Investigate the influence of strand size on thin plates warpage.
- 2) Develop strand alignment system to minimize the user variability.

Material

Material	Strand size	Dimensions (mm)
TenCate CF/PEEK UD tape	Large	25.4 x 12.7 x 0.132
	Small	6.4 x 3.2 x 0.132

Warpage Analysis

Thin Plates Processing:

Dimensions:
100 x 100 x 2mm

Lay-up:
[0/90]_s
(large strands)

Large strands

Small strands

Results:

Warpage Measurements:

Strand size	Effective Flatness Warpage (mm)	Area Weighted Average Warpage (mm)
Large	1.770 ± 0.127	0.235 ± 0.005
Small	0.730 ± 0.057	0.073 ± 0.004

Strand Alignment

Grid Design:

Results:

Falling Heights

6.4 mm

12.8 mm

12.8 mm
(no grid)

Falling Height	Strands at -30° to +30°
6.4 mm	62%
12.8 mm	38%